

Quantum Technologies for the Internet of Military Defense Things

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Abstract—The intersection of quantum technologies with the Internet of Military Defense Things (IoMDT) represents a transformative step in modern warfare and defense strategies. This paper explores the transformative potential of quantum-enabled IoMDT in next-generation 6G network infrastructures, focusing on applications at different levels of military communication and decision-making systems. We explore key areas such as quantum-accelerated data processing for real-time intelligence, surveillance and reconnaissance, quantum-assisted AI for autonomous decision making, and advanced quantum cryptographic methods to ensure secure and tamper-proof communications. The role of quantum computing in strengthening tactical infrastructure, including secure communications networks, optimising resource allocation and advanced command and control (C2) systems, and addressing significant operational challenges, including environmental sensitivity, integration with existing military systems, scalability, and the need for cost-effective quantum hardware solutions is also explored. Through case studies and detailed analysis, we provide insights into real-world implementations and outline the future directions required to fully realize the potential of quantum technologies in military IoT applications.

Index Terms—quantum technologies, quantum networks, IoMDT, 6G.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement of next generation networks and quantum technologies has pushed new frontiers for the Internet of Military Defence Things (IoMDT), which is critical to modern defence and national security. With 6G networks offering ultra-low latency, massive connectivity and enhanced data processing, military IoT applications can operate with unprecedented speed, accuracy and resilience. However, traditional IoT technologies face significant limitations in hostile and dynamic military environments. Security threats, connectivity issues and data processing delays pose significant risks and can jeopardize mission-critical operations. Quantum technologies, which include quantum communication, quantum computing and quantum sensing, offer promising solutions to these challenges [1]. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) strengthens the security making them resistant to interception and eavesdropping, which is crucial for defense applications where data integrity is paramount [2]. Quantum computing accelerates the analysis of complex data and enables real-time decision making for autonomous systems, monitoring and predictive maintenance [3]. The integration of quantum capabilities with AI also enables advanced learning models that improve situational awareness and decision making in unpredictable environments.

The military’s adoption of IoT systems has revolutionized operational strategies, enabling data-driven approaches to improve situational awareness, logistics and decision-making. IoMDT connects various military assets such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), ground vehicles, wearables and surveillance systems, providing a comprehensive view of the battlefield in real time. Despite the benefits, IoMDT deployments face some critical challenges in contested environments where communication lines are vulnerable to cyber-attacks, jamming, and environmental interferences [4]. Standard IoT encryption methods may be insufficient against sophisticated attacks, especially in warfare contexts where adversaries have advanced cyber capabilities [5]. Quantum cryptography, in particular QKD, can remedy this by providing secure encryption protocols that cannot be decrypted or intercepted using conventional computing tools [6].

Military operations require constant innovation to counter ever more sophisticated threats. The intersection of quantum and IoT technologies in 6G networks represents a strategic leap forward that overcomes the limitations of conventional systems and paves the way for a more resilient and adaptable defense infrastructure. The remainder of this paper investigates how quantum-enabled IoMDT can redefine defense capabilities and examines deployment challenges, future trends and potential applications as given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Evaluated impact of quantum technologies on IoMDT.

Quantum-enabled IoMDT offers the following advantages: (i) Quantum cryptographic methods provide unprecedented security against cyber threats, essential for safeguarding sensitive

military data [7]. (ii) Quantum computing facilitates the rapid analysis of large, complex data sets generated by IoMDT devices, enabling predictive insights and autonomous operations that enhance tactical responses [8]. (iii) Quantum-based machine learning models accelerate the processing of IoT data, improve response times and optimize resource allocation [9].

This paper explores the intersection of quantum technologies and IoMDT, focusing on applications in Radio Access Network (RAN), core and edge infrastructures. We also address key challenges, including deployment constraints and the need for interoperability in multi-domain military networks. Finally, we look to the future and outline the potential of quantum advances to revolutionize defense systems. The integration of quantum technologies in IoMDT is in line with defence strategies that aim for robust, secure and responsive networks that work in extreme conditions (See Fig. 2). Moreover, Table I compares classical and quantum-enabled IoMDT.

II. INTELLIGENCE, SURVEILLANCE, RECONNAISSANCE AND COMMAND & CONTROL (C2) OPERATIONS

Quantum sensors enhance signal processing for IoMDT devices, allowing high precision in challenging environments like urban areas or battle zones. They leverage quantum properties like entanglement and superposition to detect weak signals with remarkable accuracy, surpassing classical sensors' abilities [10].

A. Data-Intensive Military Applications and Quantum-Accelerated Machine Learning

AI and quantum technologies form a powerful synergy within 6G networks for the IoMDT, where they enable advanced data analytics, real-time decision making and autonomous operations in highly sensitive environments. By leveraging quantum computing to accelerate AI algorithms, IoMDT systems can rapidly process massive data streams and deliver insights that improve mission effectiveness, threat detection and operational security. This integration creates a cognitive, adaptive battlefield environment that supports minimal human oversight and enables intelligent, autonomous military operations. This section explores how AI and quantum technologies interact within 6G IoMDT, with applications for anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, resource optimization and tactical decision making.

Quantum computing enables complex data processing far beyond the capacity of classical computer systems, making it ideal for real-time analysis in the military sector. For example, IoMDT devices continuously collect massive data streams from various sources - drones, sensors, satellite imagery, and wearables - creating an information-rich environment that requires intensive computing resources to analyze. Quantum algorithms can process these data streams to uncover patterns, correlations, and anomalies to support predictive analytics and early threat detection. Quantum computing also enables the acceleration of machine learning algorithms [11] and thus the rapid analysis of large data sets generated by IoMDT devices. Quantum-accelerated algorithms such as quantum

support vector machines (QSVMs) and quantum neural networks (QNNs) improve AI models' processing speed and accuracy in detecting patterns and anomalies. For example, quantum-enhanced machine learning algorithms can analyze sensor data in real time to predict equipment failures, enabling predictive maintenance that extends the operational lifespan of military assets in the field, or a QSVM can analyze real-time video images from drones or surveillance sensors to detect potential threats or unusual activity. This rapid data processing enables the military to respond more effectively to threats. It makes QSVMs and QNNs valuable tools for real-time threat assessment and anomaly detection in high-risk environments.

B. Real-Time Threat Detections

Quantum AI hybrid models provide greater accuracy in threat detection by combining quantum computers' data processing capabilities with AI's pattern recognition capabilities [12]. These models can process vast amounts of real-time surveillance data and detect threats such as hostile movements, cyberattacks or hidden explosives. For example, a quantum-based AI model that analyzes data from IoMDT surveillance sensors could detect patterns indicative of enemy troop movements, enabling a rapid response. Hybrid quantum AI models can also adapt and improve their threat detection capabilities over time, providing robust security for IoMDT networks.

C. Environmental Data Analysis & Adverse Event Prediction

Quantum-enabled AI enables IoMDT systems to analyze environmental data from various sources, e.g. satellite imagery, meteorological sensors and UAV reconnaissance. This analysis can help predict unfavorable events, such as extreme weather, that could affect operations. Quantum-assisted AI can also support battlefield adaptation by analyzing terrain data so that military planners can make informed decisions about maneuvering troops and equipment [13]. For example, AI-powered quantum algorithms can evaluate complex weather patterns and predict severe storms or sandstorms, allowing forces to adapt their strategy and minimize risk. This predictive capability can be critical in regions with rapidly changing weather conditions that could otherwise disrupt operations. Military RAN environments are vulnerable to deliberate jamming by adversaries attempting to disrupt communications. Quantum communication protocols offer a solution by creating highly resilient channels that are less susceptible to interference. Quantum states used in QKD, for example, are very sensitive to changes and allow for immediate detection of jamming attempts. Furthermore, quantum entanglement can generate non-local correlations that can be used to establish alternative communication channels when a primary channel is compromised. This improves the reliability and robustness of 6G-capable IoMDT systems.

D. Quantum-Enhanced AI for Autonomous Decision-Making

Combining quantum computing and AI at the edge enables military IoT systems to make complex, autonomous decisions in the field. Quantum-enabled AI can process and interpret IoT

Fig. 2: Quantum channels for on IoMDT can be used in combat field for ISR and C2 operations and with quantum computing enabled tactical edge.

Feature	Classical IoMDT	Quantum-Enabled IoMDT
Communication Security	Relies on conventional cryptographic techniques (e.g., RSA, AES). Vulnerable to advanced decryption methods.	Uses QKD for secure communication, ensuring data integrity against future quantum attacks.
Data Processing Speed	Limited by classical computing and network bandwidth.	Quantum computing allows for faster processing of complex data and faster optimization of military strategies.
Network Scalability	Scalable with existing infrastructure but limited by classical hardware and protocol bottlenecks.	Enhanced scalability using quantum networks, which can handle vast amounts of data in more secure and efficient ways.
Interoperability	Limited by legacy systems and hardware compatibility.	Quantum technologies may initially face integration challenges but promise better cross-system interoperability through secure quantum communication protocols.
Latency	Typically lower latency with current technology but susceptible to bottlenecks as demand grows.	Quantum networks promise ultra-low latency, especially for time-sensitive military applications (e.g., real-time surveillance).
Encryption Strength	Dependent on existing encryption algorithms, which could be compromised by quantum computers in the future.	Quantum encryption (e.g., QKD) offers theoretically unbreakable encryption, resistant to quantum computing threats.
Reliability	Relies on traditional error correction methods and redundancy in classical networks.	Quantum error correction is more complex but can offer higher reliability by overcoming current network vulnerabilities.
Data Integrity	Subject to interception, alteration, or hacking (though mitigated by traditional encryption).	Provides provable data integrity using quantum states, which are impossible to clone or intercept without detection.
Communication Distance	Limited by signal loss and network congestion over long distances.	Quantum repeaters can extend the distance of secure quantum communications over large-scale areas, crucial for military operations across vast terrains.
Energy Efficiency	Can be energy-intensive due to classical hardware and signal processing demands.	Quantum communications and computation have the potential for higher energy efficiency, though still in development stages.
Resilience to Cyber Attacks	Vulnerable to cyberattacks, especially with emerging quantum computing capabilities.	Quantum systems offer superior resilience against cyberattacks, including denial of service and man-in-the-middle attacks, through quantum-resistant protocols.

TABLE I: DETAILED COMPARISON OF CLASSICAL VS. QUANTUM ENABLED INTERNET OF MILITARY DEFENCE THINGS

data at unprecedented speeds, allowing autonomous systems to adapt to changing conditions on the battlefield without human intervention. For example, a robotic unit equipped with IoMDT could navigate independently in unknown terrain and develop a strategy by quickly processing real-time data and identifying optimal routes or potential threats. Quantum algorithms accelerate such calculations and provide the AI with the necessary computing power to evaluate huge data sets and make informed decisions quickly.

III. QUANTUM COMPUTING FOR TACTICAL INFRASTRUCTURE OF MILITARY THINGS

A. Tactical Communication Network

Quantum-assisted beamforming and multiple input multiple output (MIMO) systems could also revolutionize signal directionality and transmission efficiency in the 6G RAN. In scenarios where IoMDT devices rely on precise, directional communication, such as coordination between swarms of drones or ground vehicles, quantum beamforming can dynamically adjust signal direction, improving efficiency and

reducing interference [14]. Quantum superposition can enable enhanced MIMO configurations that allow simultaneous communication with multiple IoMDT devices, improving real-time data exchange in rapidly evolving combat scenarios. Quantum networks, especially at the edge, ensure ultra-low latency data transmission, essential for time-critical military operations. Quantum networks enable entanglement-based communication protocols that enable instantaneous data exchange between interconnected IoMDT devices and ensure minimal latency even across distributed systems. This is particularly beneficial for autonomous systems such as drones, ground vehicles and robots, which rely on real-time data to operate efficiently in dynamic combat scenarios. For example, if a drone detects a potential threat, this data can be instantly relayed to nearby ground units via quantum communication channels, giving them immediate situational awareness. By deploying quantum nodes in edge networks, the military defence can achieve robust, real-time operational capabilities essential for battlefield environments where traditional computers can falter under heavy data loads.

B. Quantum-Enhanced Optimization in Resource Allocation

Resource optimization is important in military logistics, where supplies, equipment and personnel must be efficiently distributed across battlefields. Quantum optimization algorithms at the core level can solve complex logistical problems involving numerous variables and constraints, such as the dynamic allocation of fuel, ammunition and medical supplies in response to real-time changes in demand. For example, a 6G core network that supports quantum computing can analyze data from multiple supply chain sources, including IoT sensors and logistics systems, to optimize delivery routes and prioritize supplies based on urgency and proximity to the front line [15]. Such optimization ensures that resources are deployed efficiently, reducing downtime and supporting sustained combat power. Interoperability between the core and edge layers is essential for the seamless operation of military IoT systems, especially in joint operations where multinational forces may use different IoT architectures. Quantum networks enable interoperability by providing standardized communication protocols and improving data exchange between distributed systems [16]. For example, a quantum network connects core and edge nodes in a multi-domain environment, allowing command centers to access tactical data from the edge, regardless of the operational context. This interoperability is crucial for collaborative missions where joint forces depend on a unified information platform for cohesive planning.

C. Command & Control (C2) Operations

Integrating quantum technologies into the core and edge layers of 6G networks offers significant advances in data processing, transmission and operational efficiency for military IoT applications. These improvements, achieved through quantum computing, quantum networking and quantum-enabled artificial intelligence, enable rapid analysis of massive data sets, low-latency communication and real-time decision-making in highly sensitive and time-critical environments. This section explores how quantum capabilities in the 6G core and at the network's edge enhance predictive analytics, threat detection, autonomous operations and resource optimization in military IoT [17]. Reinforcement learning, a branch of AI in which agents learn by interacting with their environment, can be significantly accelerated by quantum computing, enabling autonomous mission planning for IoMDT devices. Quantum reinforcement learning algorithms, such as quantum-reinforced Q-learning, can rapidly explore and evaluate multiple tactical options and optimize mission parameters to increase real-time success rates. For example, an autonomous military vehicle equipped with quantum reinforcement learning could adjust its route based on environmental and situational data, minimize threat exposure, and optimize fuel consumption. This capability supports adaptive mission planning for unmanned systems and increases their effectiveness in dynamic battlefields.

IV. QUANTUM-BASED SECURITY IN IoMDTS

In military IoMDT, QKD can be used within 6G RAN to secure communication links between command centers, troops on the front line and unmanned vehicles. For example, a soldier in a hostile area can communicate with a command center via QKD-encrypted channels, ensuring that sensitive tactical information remains confidential even if adversaries attempt to intercept it [18]. Such secure connections are crucial for operations in multi-domain operations where fast and secure communication between air, sea and land units is essential. Another promising application within the quantum-based RAN is Quantum Secure Direct Communication (QSDC), which enables the direct transmission of information without key distribution and thus circumvents conventional security gaps. QSDC can encode information directly into quantum states, enabling a higher level of security when transmitting commands or data to IoMDT devices on the battlefield [10]. For example, a command center can send mission-critical instructions directly to a UAV, with QSDC ensuring that only the intended device can receive and decode the information to protect it from cyber threats. Quantum entanglement, a property in which particles remain connected in such a way that the state of one particle directly affects the state of another, can also be used to improve the security of device-to-device communications. Entanglement enables IoMDT devices to establish highly secure connections that cannot be manipulated or intercepted. In the military domain, entangled particles could be distributed to IoMDT devices to enable secure communications between soldiers, vehicles and UAVs, ensuring that communications on the battlefield remain private and resilient to interception. This secure device-to-device communication is critical to ensuring the integrity of missions in unpredictable and hostile environments.

In the military domain, unauthorized access to IoMDT devices can have serious consequences, such as compromising intelligence or gaining unauthorized control of critical assets. Quantum-based authentication methods such as Quantum Digital Signatures (QDS) offer a high level of security for the authentication of devices and users in the IoMDT network. QDS uses quantum states to create tamper-proof digital signatures that verify the identity of a user or device without relying on traditional cryptographic methods, which can be vulnerable to certain cyberattacks. QDS could be used, for example, to secure access to IoMDT-equipped UAVs and ensure that only authenticated military personnel can operate the drone or change its mission parameters. Quantum technologies provide a robust layer of security for IoMDT systems that is critical in the defense sector, where data breaches can have catastrophic consequences. Quantum cryptography, particularly QKD, provides secure communication channels that are theoretically unbreakable, protecting the integrity and confidentiality of sensitive military data. Quantum-based security mechanisms such as advanced authentication, anomaly detection and secure direct communication increase the resilience of IoMDT systems against cyber threats and unauthorized access. These quantum

technologies are critical to maintaining secure communications and protecting data in next generation military networks.

Quantum anomaly detection systems enhance IoMDT network security by utilizing quantum machine learning algorithms to analyze large data sets in real time. They identify patterns and anomalies that may signal cyber threats. For instance, such a system can monitor IoMDT traffic to promptly recognize unusual patterns that might suggest a cyberattack, allowing military defense systems to thwart breaches proactively. This ensures the resilience of IoMDT devices in contested environments. The overall Quantum security techniques are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Quantum based security techniques for IoMDT.

V. DEPLOYMENT CHALLENGES

Quantum technologies in IoMDTs face significant technical, logistical, and economic challenges, as shown in Fig. 4. These arise from quantum systems' unique requirements, such as sensitivity to environmental conditions, the need for specialized hardware, and complex integration with existing military infrastructure. Quantum devices, especially quantum communication systems such as QKD and QSDC, require highly controlled environments to function optimally. Quantum states are extremely sensitive to temperature fluctuations, electromagnetic interference and vibrations — conditions that are difficult to manage on the battlefield. For example, maintaining the stability of quantum entanglement in harsh environments such as deserts or mountainous regions is a major challenge. Specialized enclosures with advanced temperature and vibration control may be required to protect quantum devices from environmental influences, making them difficult to move and increasing deployment costs. Although quantum cryptography is very secure, quantum systems are still vulnerable to certain attacks, such as side-channel attacks and denial-of-service (DoS) attacks. Side-channel attacks exploit physical vulnerabilities in quantum devices, such as laser timing or power consumption, to extract information about the quantum states. In addition, military IoMDT deployments in contested areas may face DoS attacks aimed at disrupting quantum communication channels. To mitigate these risks, additional security measures such as physical shielding and robust surveillance systems are required, which increase the complexity and cost of quantum IoMDT deployments.

Quantum systems are highly susceptible to noise and external interference, which can disrupt quantum states and lead to data loss. The effective use of quantum technologies in IoMDT requires advanced error correction techniques to maintain data integrity in hostile environments. Quantum error correction (QEC) codes, such as surface codes and topological codes, are under development but require extensive computational resources that can be challenging to implement on portable, battlefield deployable quantum devices. In addition, shielding quantum devices from radio frequency interference (RFI) and electromagnetic interference (EMI) requires robust enclosures, which can increase the footprint and reduce the mobility of IoMDT systems.

The integration of quantum communication and computing systems into the existing military infrastructure requires significant adaptation of hardware, protocols and interoperability standards. Existing military IoT devices and networks are typically designed for conventional cryptographic methods and classical computing, which are not inherently compatible with quantum systems. For example, deploying QKD in an established 6G network requires customized hardware and quantum-compatible encryption protocols that differ from conventional methods. In addition, achieving interoperability between quantum-enabled IoMDT systems and standard military communication networks requires new protocol standards that are still at an early stage of development.

Quantum technology is still emerging and comes with high manufacturing and maintenance costs. Devices like superconducting processors, ion trap systems, and QKD units are costly to produce and operate. For military IoMDT deployments, robust quantum hardware must endure operational conditions, adding to costs. This high expense hampers the scalability of these technologies in IoMDT, as defense budgets may not cover widespread quantum hardware deployment. Additionally, building and maintaining quantum infrastructure demands significant investments, which some military budgets may not support. The absence of standardized quantum communication and computing protocols complicates quantum technologies' integration into military IoMDT systems. While protocols like BB84 for QKD exist, comprehensive standards for integrating quantum systems into 6G IoT networks are still in development [19]. Military applications need tailored protocols for compatibility, security, and interoperability between quantum

Fig. 4: Challenges in IoMDT quantum technology deployment.

and classical systems. The lack of such standards hinders widespread quantum technology adoption, as inconsistencies might lead to vulnerabilities or operational challenges in military IoMDT deployments.

Quantum systems tend to be large, fragile and complex, making them difficult to miniaturize for portable military applications. Current quantum hardware, such as cryogenic systems for superconducting qubits, is unsuitable for mobile platforms such as UAVs or soldier-mounted IoMDT devices. Although there has been progress in compact quantum devices, further research is needed to make these systems lightweight, durable and energy efficient for field use. Developing mobile quantum hardware that can withstand harsh conditions without compromising performance remains a major technical challenge. Quantum communication systems, especially those based on QKD, have a limited range due to photon losses over long distances, which limits their use in long-range military networks [20]. Current ground-based QKD systems typically operate over a range of tens to hundreds of kilometers, making them impractical for long-range communications without quantum repeaters or satellite links. To overcome this limitation, satellite-based QKD and quantum repeaters are currently being developed. However, these technologies are still at the experimental stage and face challenges in terms of cost, implementation and reliability in dynamic environments [21]. For quantum networks to be used in military applications, they must support multiple devices over long distances while ensuring secure synchronization. Quantum networks require precise timing and synchronization, as even small delays can disrupt the transmission of quantum states, leading to data loss or desynchronization. In a combat scenario, synchronization of quantum nodes across dispersed IoMDT devices such as UAVs, ground vehicles and soldier wearables is a challenge. Achieving reliable synchronization over long distances with mobile quantum nodes also requires innovative solutions such as satellite-based quantum repeaters, which are still under research and development.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This paper establishes a foundation for understanding quantum technologies' transformative role in defense, particularly in IoMDT. We explore quantum applications and security protocols, illustrating how quantum computing, communications, and AI can revolutionize military operations with enhanced speed, security, and real-time decision-making. The integration of quantum technologies into IoMDT systems significantly improves operational efficiency, situational awareness, and mission success in high-risk environments. QKD and QSDC offer secure communication channels essential for protecting military data. Quantum AI enables rapid data analysis and predictive insights for mission planning, maintenance, and threat detection. With advancements in quantum and 6G technologies, IoMDT defense applications will expand. Future research should enhance quantum communication resilience in unpredictable combat scenarios and develop lightweight quantum components for harsh environments. Initial deployments indi-

cate that ensuring interoperability between quantum-enabled and legacy systems is crucial for seamless transitions and data integrity.

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